

Exploring the Effectiveness of *Babad Pasirluhur* Story to Teach Past Simple and Students' Perspective on Its Usage

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ABSTRACT

The purposes of this study were to investigate the effectiveness of a local story entitled Babad Pasirluhur for teaching past simple and students' voices on its usage. Therefore, the method employed was quasi-experimental research, and the instruments used were a multiple-choice item test and a closed questionnaire. The result revealed that Babad Pasirluhur story was effective to teach past simple because the value of Mann Whitney test result (97.5) was lower than Mann Whitney table (324). The significance level was 0.05. Furthermore, the result of the questionnaire showed that most of the students had positive responses toward Babad Pasirluhur. Overall, a local story entitled Babad Pasirluhur was effective to teach past simple, and the students mostly gave positive responses to the story.

1. Introduction

Grammar is one of English elements considered as essential yet difficult. In English grammar, there are many aspects discussed, and one of them is tenses. According to Collins (2017), tense is the verb form which shows whether you are referring to the past or present. One of English tenses commonly used in daily life is past simple. Azar (2002) explains that the simple past is used to talk about activities or situations that began and ended in the past. Some adverbs of time used in past simple are yesterday, last night, two minutes ago, and in 2010.

Mastering past simple is essential yet difficult for English learners. Aniuranti and Rizkina (2019) state that past simple is quite difficult to be mastered due to several reasons. First, some students are still confused about form of past simple and past participle. Second, they are also confused about the functions of past simple.

The difficulty of learning tenses probably encounters by most of Indonesian learners including the students of SMK Diponegoro 3 Kedungbanteng. They still had problem in

learning past simple. For solving this problem, the teacher may use effective teaching approaches, methods, techniques or media. According to Brown in Indah (2019), using variety of media will increase the probability that students will learn more, retain better that they learn, and improve their performance of the skill they are expected to develop.

One of teaching media for teaching past simple is *Babad Pasirluhur* story. This story has possibility as teaching media of past simple due to several reasons. First, in Banyumas, *Babad Pasirluhur* is a legend that is well known by *Banyumas* residents especially in surrounding of *Baturaden* such as *Kedungbanteng*, *Sumbang*, and *Purwokerto Selatan*. Furthermore, *Babad Pasirluhur* story has many past simple forms which can give students some experiences for applying the theory in the class to the story. Therefore, using *Babad Pasirluhur* story in teaching past simple may assist students to focus in past simple material because they know the meaning of the story.

This possibility still requires a scientific examination. Therefore, a quasi-experimental study was conducted to find out the effectiveness of *Babad Pasirluhur* study. Besides, the researchers were concerned to find students' perspective toward this story.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Grammar

Grammar that is also well-known as structure is commonly defined as the process of constructing words into larger elements like phrases and sentences. Harmer (2002) points out that grammar is a description of the rules for forming sentences, including an account of the meaning that these forms convey. Nunan (2004) states that grammar is the rules of languages that show how sentences are formed or how words are inflected. Aniuranti and Rizkina (2019) add that grammar is commonly known as the rules of arranging words into sentences.

2.2 Simple Past

According to Azar (2002), the simple past indicates an activity or situation that began and ended at a particular time in the past, example: yesterday, last night, two minutes ago, in 2010. Nindya (2017) explains that the simple past tense describes an action which happened in the time before the present time and is no longer happening. Simple past tense is also used if the activity happened completely in the past even though the time is not mentioned. Murphy (2019) mentions some examples of sentences using past simple such as I enjoyed the party a lot, did you enjoy it? and I didn't buy anything because I didn't have any money".

2.3 Narrative Text

According to Nindya (2017), narrative text is a type of essay that tells a story or a series of events in which they occur. Ningsih and Rosa (2019) also state that narrative text is a story that has complication or problematic events and it tries to find the resolutions to solve the problem. Pruba in Ningsih and Rosa (2019) explains that a narrative is some kinds of retelling, something that happened and tells a story. Then, Syarif in Susanti (2017) says that narrative text is the story that happened in the past.

There are several kinds of narrative story. According to Crown (2013), there are four types of narrative story. They are as follows.

a. Legend

Narrative legend provides information about the way particular people lived and what they believed. The generic structure of legend is with one episode told after another, for example as the phases of a journey or the stages of an ongoing battle. Some legends tell the whole life story or their hero as a series of linked episodes, each one may be a story in its own right. Common structures include chronological episodes, journey stories, sequential stories, life stories and community histories. The language features are very similar to those of myths: rich (evocative vocabulary), memorable language use, use of rhythm and repetition techniques, formulaic openings and endings and imagery (smile, metaphor and symbolism).

b. Fable

Narrative fable is a story that tells the life of animals that behave like humans. Narrative fable can be called moral stories because it contains messages that relate to morals. The structure is typically the simplest kind of narrative with a beginning, a complication and a resolution. Two characters (often animals) meet, an event occurs and they go on their way with one of them having learned an important lesson about life.

c. Science Fiction

Science fiction is a fiction that speculates about the future. The writer must use description carefully when the writer wants the readers to imagine something that they have never seen. The generic structure of science fiction can use any of the varied structures typical of narrative. The setting is often a time in future so may use structures that play with the time sequence, such as flashbacks and time travel. Science fiction typically includes detail about the way that people might live in the future, predicting in creative and imaginative way how technology might advance.

d. Fairy Tale

Fairy tale usually has folkloric characters such as goblins, fairies, elves, dwarves, giants, trolls, or gnomes, and are usually followed by the magicians and spells. Fairy tale is written by using phrases that have a strong rhyme or rhythm or another kind of pattern. Fairy tale is also written by using different styles of language for the human beings and the characters from the fairy world when they speak to make a strong contrast between them. The structure of fairy tale is mostly typically a recount in chronological order, when events retell what happened to a main character that came into contact with the 'fairy world'. Often the hero or heroine is searching for something (a home, love acceptance, wealth, wisdom) and in many tale dreams are fulfilled with a little help from magic. Fairy tale endings (where everything turns out for the best) are common but many fairy tales are darker and have a sad ending. The formulaic sentences of fairy tale are used "once upon time..., there was once a..., long ago in the..., it came to past...".

Furthermore, narrative story has some general features. According to Yani in Susanti (2017), there are six language features of narrative text such as:

1. Using past simple
2. Time signal such as last, a long time ago, one upon time, etc.
3. Time conjunction such as when, then, suddenly, etc.
4. Specific character such as Cinderella, Aladin, Alibaba, etc.

5. Action verb such as killed, dug, walked, etc.
6. Direct speech such as (Snow White said, "My name is Snow White"), and the direct speech uses simple present tense.

2.4 Babad Pasirluhur

Babad Pasirluhur is a local story from Banyumas regency. This story belongs to legend due to the characteristics of this story. In *Babad Pasirluhur* story, there are many language features such as past tense (held, went, etc.), adverb of time (once upon a time, one day, etc.), specific character (Banyak Cotro, Siliwangi, Dewi Ciptoroso, Reksonoto, etc.), action verb (chased, commanded, etc.), direct speech ("Well, Banyak Cotro, if that what's you want". said *Prabu* Siliwangi) and the generic structure in *Babad Pasirluhur* story such as orientation, complication, resolution and reorientation.

In this research, the writers wanted to find out the possibility of this local story as a teaching media of past simple. The team assumed that this story might be used to teach past simple due to some reasons. They are as follows:

- a. The students have already understood the main contain of the story since this story is local story from Banyumas. This condition may give the students time to understand more about other elements such as language features of the story.
- b. Past simple is used a lot in this story since this story belongs to legend.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Participants

The research design employed was quasi experimental research. According to Sugiyono (2014) quasi experimental design is an experimental research developed because there is difficulty to control the independent variables that can influence the experiment. This study used quasi experimental because there were external variables that could not be controlled by the researchers. The experimental group is a group who gets treatment for using *Babad Pasirluhur* story in narrative text material, meanwhile the control group is a group who get treatment of using Conventional Method for teaching past simple.

The research subject of this study was the first grade students of SMK Diponegoro 3 Kedungbanteng. There were 24 students from X AKL (*Akuntansi dan Keuangan Lembaga*) as experimental group, and 27 students from X OTKP (*Otomatisasi dan Tata Kelola Perkantoran*) as control group. These two groups were chosen since they were considered to have equal ability in English.

3.2 Instruments

In this study, there were two instruments used called test and questionnaire. Here is the explanation of each instrument.

1. Test

In this study, the test was used to measure students' mastery of past simple. The test was in form of multiple choice item adapted from several English grammar books called Azar (1996 and 2002), Hewings (2005), Collins (2017) and Murphy (2019). In doing the adaptation process, the researchers consider several theories related to multiple choices. Both of classes, experimental and control group, were

given the same pre-test and post-test about the past simple. There are 30 items of multiple choices for each test.

2. Questionnaire

According to Reiger (2012), questionnaires can be used in various subject areas and for a variety of purposes. She also explains that the use of questioning is to determine what students know about a particular outcome or goal in a unit of study. In this research, there were five questions that have to be answered by the students. The data from the questionnaire was conducted to strengthen the data. The students only answered "yes" or "no" for each question.

3.3 Data Analysis Procedures

In this research, the researchers used some ways to do analyzing the data, as the follows:

1. Normality test

Normality test is a test that is done to know whether that the data is in normal distribution or not. The researchers used the Liliefors test for knowing the normality of data because Liliefors test is more sensitive than Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. It is based on the Nasrum in Widana and Muliani (2020) that shows the station of Hubert Whitman Liliefors who states that Kolmogorov-Smirnov table is valid as the standard for normality test if the data observation is from function of continue distribution. After getting the L_o , it is compared to $L_t \alpha 5\%$. The characteristic of Liliefors test as the following:

- a. If $L_o < L_t$ = data is normal
- b. If $L_o > L_t$ = data is not normal

According to Widana and Muliani (2020) and Rinaldi et al., (2020), the steps for doing Liliefors test are as follows:

- a. Sorting the data from the lowest until the highest
- b. Determining the cumulative frequency
- c. Determining the Zi value

$$Z_i = \frac{x_i - \bar{x}}{s}$$

Where :

Z_i : the coefficient

x_i : the score of sample

\bar{x} : mean

s : standard deviation

The formula of mean (\bar{x}) in Excel used "= AVERAGE(... :)" and in manual as the following formula:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x_i}{n}$$

Where :

\bar{x} : the coefficient

$\sum x_i$: total sample score

n : sample

The formula of standard deviation (S) in Excel used “=STDEV(.... :)” and in manual as the following formula:

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}}$$

Where :

S : the coefficient

$\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2$: total $(x_i - \bar{x})^2$

n : sample

- d. Determining the F (Zi) value with using Z table score
- e. Determining the S (Zi) value with the formula:

$$S(Z_i) = \frac{f_{cum}}{n}$$

Where :

S (Zi) : the coefficient

f_{cum} : frequency cumulative

n : sample

- f. Determining the value of $L = |F(Z_i) - S(Z_i)|$
- g. Choosing the high value of $L = |F(Z_i) - S(Z_i)|$
- h. Determining the value of L_{table}
- i. Comparing with the L_{table}

2. Homogeneity test

Homogeneity test is done to know whether the sample was homogenous or not. The test used in this research is F test. After getting the F_{count} , it will be compared to $F_t \alpha 5\%$. The characteristic of F test is as the follows:

- a. If $F_{count} < F_t$ = data is homogenous
- b. If $F_{count} > F_t$ = data is not homogenous

According to Budiwanto (2017), the steps for doing F test are as follows:

- a. Counting the standard deviation quadrate of data used the formula:

$$S_x^2 = \sqrt{\frac{n \cdot \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2}{n(n-1)}} \quad S_y^2 = \sqrt{\frac{n \cdot \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2}{n(n-1)}}$$

- b. Counting the F_{count} of experimental group (x) and control group (y) used the formula:

$$F = \frac{S_{higher}}{S_{lower}}$$

- c. Comparing the F_{count} to F_t based on the distribution F table after knowing the numerator and denominator using $n - 1$.

3. Hypothesis test

After doing normality and homogeneity test, the researchers continued the hypothesis test used Mann Whitney test. Suyanto and Gio (2017) states that Mann Whitney test is nonparametric test that used to know the differences of two

independents samples. It is done if the results of normality test and homogeneity test are not fulfilled.

The followings were the formula of hypothesis tests and the comparing for both of tests. According to Suyanto and Gio (2017), the formula of Mann Whitney test:

$$U_1 = n_1 n_2 + \frac{(n_1)(n_1+1)}{2} - R_1$$

$$U_2 = n_1 n_2 + \frac{(n_2)(n_2+1)}{2} - R_2$$

$$U_{\text{count}} = \text{minimum}(U_1, U_2)$$

Where:

U = coefficient

n = sample

R = ranking of the sample

For determining the hypothesis, there are two criteria. Here are the categories.

- a. H_0 is accepted if $U_{\text{count}} > U_{\text{table}}$
- b. H_1 is accepted if $U_{\text{count}} \leq U_{\text{table}}$

For determining U_{table} with more than 20 samples, the team used the formula based on the theory from Nugroho (2008). Here is the formula.

$$W_p = \frac{nm}{2} + Z_p \sqrt{\frac{nm(n+m+1)}{12}}$$

Where:

W_p = coefficient

n = sample (n_1)

m = sample (n_2)

Z_p = value of normal standard cumulative distribution

For determining Z_p , the researchers used Z_p formula based on the theory from Suyanto and Gio (2017). Here is the formula.

$$Z_p = \frac{U_{\text{count}} - \left[\frac{n_1 n_2}{2} \right]}{\sqrt{\frac{n_1 n_2 (n_1 + n_2 + 1)}{12}}}$$

Where:

Z_p = coefficient

n = sample

U_{count} = value of Mann Whitney test

For analyzing the data, the researcher used the formula as follow:

$$P = \frac{FA}{N} \times 100\%$$

Where:

4.3 Hypothesis test

The results from the normality test and homogeneity test showed that Mann Whitney test were needed. It was because the two requirements for using t-test did not accomplish. The data distribution was not normal.

The hypothesis test of using Mann Whitney test states that if $U_{count} < U_{table}$, H_1 was accepted and H_0 was rejected, it can be said that the result affects in increasing students' ability to understand the past simple through using *Babad Pasirluhur* story. In other words, if $U_{count} > U_{table}$, H_1 was rejected and H_0 was accepted, it can be said that the result does not affect in increasing students' ability to understand the past simple through using *Babad Pasirluhur* story. The results of hypothesis testing conducted using Mann Whitney test can be seen as follows:

Table 3. The results of Mann Whitney test

N of experimental class	24 students
N of control class	27 students
R_1 (Ranking of experimental post-test)	850.5
R_2 (Ranking of control post-test)	475.5
U_1 (Value of experimental post-test)	97.5
U_2 (Value of control post-test)	550.5
U_{count} (Value of Mann Whitney test)	= $\min(U_1:U_2)$ = $\min(97.5:550.5)$ = 97.5
$U_{table} (0,05)$	324
$Z_{table} (-4,27)$	0.000
Hypothesis: $U_{count} < U_{table}$ $97.5 < 324$	H_1 was accepted and H_0 was rejected.

Based on the table above, the U_{count} (97.5) was lower than the U_{table} (324) with the significance value 0.05. It proved that H_1 was accepted and H_0 was rejected. Therefore, it could be concluded that using *Babad Pasirluhur* story was effective for teaching past simple.

4.4 Students' Perception of Using *Babad Pasirluhur* Story

After doing the post-test, the students were asked to complete the questionnaire prepared. The purpose of giving questionnaire was to find out the students' perception about using *Babad Pasirluhur* story for teaching past simple. The data was acquired from distributions of questionnaire to the students at experimental class. In the questionnaire, the researcher used the simple questions for the students who could answer with choosing yes or no. The data was showed with the percentage of the answer. The questionnaire results can be seen in the following tables.

Table 4. Students' perception

No	Question	Yes	No
1	Do you feel happy to learn Past Simple with Babad Pasirluhur story?	91.67 %	8.33 %
2	Can Babad Pasirluhur story increase your understanding about Past Simple?	100%	0%
3	Can Babad Pasirluhur story motivate you to learn English especially Past Simple material?	83.33 %	16.67 %
4	Does Babad Pasirluhur story provide a positive atmosphere in teaching learning process of Past Simple material?	79.17 %	20.83 %
5	Is using Babad Pasirluhur story for teaching Past Simple needed to be applied continuously?	100%	0%

Based on the table above, there were several important conclusions. First, most of the students (91.67%) felt happy to study past simple through the story. Second, all the students (100%) said that *Babad Pasirluhur* could improve their understanding of past simple. Third, most of the students (83.33%) said that the story motivated them to learn more about English especially past simple. Fourth, most of the students (79.17%) agreed that *Babad Pasirluhur* created positive atmosphere during the teaching and learning process. Fifth, all the students (100%) agreed to use the story as a teaching medium of past simple. Overall, the results of questionnaire showed that the students gave positive sounds toward *Babad Pasirluhur* story.

5. Discussion

Based on the data analysis, the study revealed that *Babad Pasirluhur* story was effective to teach past simple. The Mann Whitney test score was 97.5, and the value of Mann Whitney table at significance level 0.05 was 324 ($U_{score} < U_{table}$). This calculation showed that *Babad Pasirluhur* story was effective. The story utilized in this research helped the students to understand the concept of past simple. This finding is in line with the theories from the previous studies about using story for teaching past simple. Pardede (2011) underlines that stories help students to learn grammar, and stories can be used for both obtaining and illustrating grammar points. Biswas and Anis (2017) also point out that students will certainly appreciate and respond to the efforts of including them in the storytelling process, but they will enjoy learning grammar through stories.

In addition, *Babad Pasirluhur* as a local story from Banyumas contains of substantial elements of past simple. Here are the instances.

1. Verbal Sentences (S + Past form)
 - a. *Prabu* Siliwangi and *Dewi* Kumudaningsih got married.
 - b. One day, *Prabu* Siliwangi held a meeting at his palace.
 - c. After several days, he arrived at Pasirluhur Regency.
2. Nominal Sentences (S + To Be + Complement)
 - a. Once upon a time, there was a kingdom named Pajajaran.
 - b. They were Banyak Cotro and Banyak Ngampar.
3. Past form of Irregular Verbs
Went, got, held, met, came, dove, forgave, said, etc.

Furthermore, the learning atmosphere in both classes seemed different. In control class, the students looked uninterested and unmotivated. This situation was probably caused by the conventional method of teaching past simple. Meanwhile, in experimental class, the students looked happy and motivated during the teaching and learning process. It could be also seen from the questionnaire results. The result showed that the Yes answer is more dominant than the No answer in the experimental class. It is because students felt happy and got the motivation in learning past simple after using the story. This result was in line with several theories. Biswas and Anis (2017) state that rightly selected stories provide a context and motivation for learning grammar. Mufidah et al., (2020) also argue that for making students interested in teaching and learning process, the teacher may use learning media. Learning media contributes to the students' motivation in teaching and learning process. One of the media is narrative text especially local story.

In conclusion, *Babad Pasirluhur* as local story form Banyumas was effective to teach past simple at Vocational High School level. The statistic calculation revealed the significant effect of the implementation of that story. Furthermore, the results from the questionnaire also showed positive perception toward the usage of *Babad Pasirluhur*.

6. Conclusion

Every English teacher has responsibility to help their students accomplish the learning objectives arranged. One of the suggested ways of teaching English is using effective teaching media like stories. *Babad Pasirluhur* story as the local story of Banyumas has possibilities as a teaching media for troublesome element like past simple. Therefore, this study employed quasi experimental research to test this possibility. After conducting the study, the results reveals some essential conclusions. First, *Babad Pasirluhur* story as local story was effective to teach past simple. The result showed that Mann Whitney test was lower than Mann Whitney table ($97.5 < 324$). H_0 was rejected and H_1 was accepted. Second, most of the students gave positive responses toward the usage of this story. The highest percentage of each item was in Yes option.

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